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SURVEY

Quantitative Evaluation of Repeatability in Medical Microwave Imaging: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT Medical microwave imaging (MMWI) prototypes have demonstrated potential in various clinical applications. For successful clinical translation, these systems must be reliable and yield consistent results, that is, they must demonstrate high repeatability. This systematic review critically appraises the existing literature on repeatability in MMWI, with particular attention to the protocols, metrics, and outcomes reported. A systematic search of Scopus, IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, and PubMed was conducted on April 29th 2025, identifying 21 studies that quantitatively evaluated repeatability in MMWI. Two reviewers independently performed full-text screening and data extraction, with disagreements resolved through consultation with a third reviewer. Descriptive analyses were performed using tables and figures to characterise study design, methodologies, and findings. Considerable heterogeneity was observed in sample size, imaging protocols, and the selection of repeatability metrics. Almost all studies were restricted to breast imaging applications. Frequently reported sources of variability included subject repositioning, tissue changes, and hardware-related factors. Although most studies reported acceptable repeatability, the absence of standardised protocols and metrics limits cross-study comparison and the establishment of benchmarks. The review concludes with recommendations to harmonise approaches that contribute to accelerate the clinical translation of MMWI systems.

INDEX TERMS Diagnosis, medical microwave imaging, metrics, repeatability, reproducibility, standardization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical microwave imaging (MMWI) has been proposed for a multitude of applications, including breast cancer detection, breast health monitoring, assessment of treatment response in breast cancer, stroke detection and monitoring, bone health monitoring, among others. MMWI uses non-ionising radiation at low power levels, which makes it particularly attractive for repeated use without causing harmful side effects. As a result, interest in its clinical potential has grown substantially. A number of MMWI prototypes have already been developed and tested in clinical trials [1], [2], [3], [4].

With increasing interest in these technologies, the next step is clinical integration — either as a complement

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to or a replacement for existing imaging modalities. For medical adoption, it is essential that MMWI systems produce consistent and reliable results. Specifically, results must be repeatable under equivalent conditions and not overly sensitive to external or system-related noise, such as temperature fluctuations or hardware drift. Systems with high repeatability are better positioned to detect clinically relevant changes in tissue, whether related to the development of pathological conditions or to responses to treatment.

Despite the growing number of experimental MMWI studies and clinical prototypes, there are currently no defined standards or no comprehensive synthesis of how repeatability is evaluated across different systems, protocols, and metrics. This lack of standardisation limits comparability across studies and hinders regulatory approval and clinical

translation. Preliminary examination of the literature suggests substantial variability in how repeatability is conceptualised and measured in MMWI studies, preventing a clear understanding of how hardware design choices, or reconstruction algorithms influence measurement repeatability, with the term often used interchangeably with reproducibility.

Following definitions of the quantitative imaging biomarkers literature [5], this review defines repeatability as the ability of a system to produce consistent results under equivalent conditions, without being overly influenced by external noise. In contrast, reproducibility refers to the ability of a system to yield comparable results when replicated in other settings — for example, in different institutions, by different operators.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no previous study has systematically examined how the repeatability of MMWI prototypes is evaluated, including the protocols and metrics used, or whether the reported systems demonstrate repeatable results. A systematic review is therefore of utmost importance to assess existing evaluation practices, and identify the main sources of variability that affect repeatability. By synthesising current approaches to assess repeatability, such a review can also provide insight into standardising strategies to improve the robustness and reliability of MMWI systems, contributing to establish the clinical efficacy of MMWI technologies and their progression from research prototypes to clinically deployable technologies.

This systematic review addresses these gaps by answering the following research questions:

R1: How has repeatability been assessed in the existing MMWI literature?

R2: Do the MMWI prototypes reported in the literature demonstrate repeatability?

II. METHODS

This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [6].

A. STUDY SELECTION

A systematic literature search was conducted to identify studies that evaluated the repeatability of microwave-based systems in biomedical or clinical contexts, including applications, but not limited to, the breast, brain, and stroke. The review focused on studies that employed quantitative metrics to assess repeatability across repeated measurements, and/or multiple sessions.

B. DATA SOURCES

A systematic search of published studies was conducted in the following databases:

- Scopus
- IEEE Xplore
- Web of Science
- PubMed

These databases were selected for their comprehensive coverage of the relevant literature in the field of medical microwave imaging, including both peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. Conference papers were included given that it is common practice in this field to present peer-reviewed work at conferences.

C. SEARCH STRATEGY

The defined search strategy included different combinations of the following concepts: microwave, imaging, signal, radar, detection, diagnosis, scanning, screening, monitoring, reproducib*, repeatab*, consisten*, simila*, variability, quatitf*, measur*, metri*, evaluat*, successive, asses*, longitudinal, over time, figure of merit, medical, breast, brain, stroke, bone, skin, and lung. The full description of the search strategy is available in the supplementary material. The search was limited to articles published in English, and no date restrictions were applied, with the search being conducted in April 29th, 2025. Duplicates were removed using Rayyan - a web based software for duplicate records removal and screening of papers in systematic reviews [7].

D. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The studies included in this systematic review met the following criteria:

- Investigated microwave-based systems, such as imaging, radar, or signal processing techniques;
- Focused on biomedical imaging or clinical diagnostic contexts, including but not limited to breast, brain, stroke, skin, bone, or lung applications;
- Assessed repeatability of results using quantitative metrics, across repeated measurements, multiple sessions, or varying subjects.

Only studies published in peer-reviewed journals or conference proceedings were considered for inclusion.

E. SOURCE OF EVIDENCE SELECTION

Selection and screening process: this step includes title and abstract screening, followed by full text screening. Both stages were performed independently by two reviewers (HL and DG). Title and abstract screening was conducted in Rayyan. The title and abstracts were assessed against the inclusion criteria with each reviewer assessing if each abstract was eligible for full text screening. Disagreements between reviewers were solved based on discussion to arrive to a consensus and when needed a third reviewer (RC) was consulted.

Data management: The management of search results was conducted using OneDrive for storage and organisation, and Zotero for reference management.

F. MAIN OUTCOMES

The main outcomes extracted from the included studies were categorised into seven groups:

- 1) Evidence of repeatability assessment, including definitions of this concept and the specific types of evaluation performed;
- 2) Quantitative metrics employed to assess repeatability (e.g., Dice coefficient, correlation coefficients);
- 3) Context of the assessment, encompassing the imaging target, use of physical phantoms, involvement of healthy volunteers or patients, and a description of the microwave system utilised;
- 4) Study design characteristics, such as the number of repeated measurements, number of subjects, and the interval between measurements;
- 5) Reported sources of variability, including system-related, operator-related, subject-related, and environment-related factors;
- 6) Reported results of the assessments, including metric values;
- 7) Prevalence or dominance of specific metrics used to evaluate repeatability.

G. DATA EXTRACTION

Data extraction was conducted independently by HL and DG using a spreadsheet in Microsoft Excel. Prior to screening the full set of included articles, a pilot test was performed on four reference studies [8], [9], [10], [11] to evaluate the appropriateness and completeness of the data extraction categories. Discrepancies in the extracted data were resolved through discussion with a third reviewer (RC).

The following variables were extracted: first author, senior author, year of publication, study objective, characteristics of the microwave imaging system, reconstruction and processing algorithms employed, study design (e.g., use of physical phantoms, healthy volunteers, or patients), sample size, clinical or biomedical application (e.g., breast, brain), definitions of repeatability, the specific metrics used to assess repeatability, type of repeatability assessment, key findings related to repeatability, and reported sources of variability.

For the purposes of this review, the type of repeatability assessment was categorised as follows:

- Test-retest: repeated measurements acquired on the same subject or phantom within a single session, under identical conditions and without intentional repositioning.
- Inter-session: repeated measurements acquired across multiple sessions, generally involving subject or phantom repositioning and/or a temporal interval between acquisitions.

H. RISK OF BIASES IN INDIVIDUAL STUDIES

Two reviewers (DG and HL) independently performed full-text screening of the studies. The results from each reviewer were discussed until a consensus was reached regarding the combination of the results. Therefore, avoiding the results to be biased towards the judgement of a single reviewer. A third reviewer (RC) was available to be consulted in the event of unresolved disagreement.

I. DATA SYNTHESIS

After completing the data extraction process, the information recorded in the individual Excel spreadsheets was polished.

A descriptive analysis was performed to synthesise information and illustrate trends in the use of quantitative metrics for repeatability assessments, reporting the main outcomes reached, including the ranges of values for the repeatability metrics obtained in each study. The results were presented in tables and figures to facilitate understanding and comparison across studies.

Repeatability metrics reported in each study were extracted and subsequently categorised according to their primary function. This categorisation was developed *post hoc* using an empirical thematic analysis of the mathematical definitions of the metrics and usage contexts, rather than being predetermined. A detailed description of each metric and its classification is provided in the Results section.

III. RESULTS

A. LITERATURE SEARCH AND STUDY SELECTION

The systematic review of the literature was conducted on April 29th 2025, in which 953 records were retrieved from the four databases screened (for more details see Supplemental material). One additional relevant study was identified through manual reference list screening. After removing duplicates, 608 abstracts were screened for eligibility based on the inclusion criteria by two reviewers (DG and HL). A total of 23 papers were selected for full-text screening. During full-text screening phase two studies were excluded due to not reporting quantitative methods to assess repeatability [12], [13]. Ultimately, 21 papers were included for data extraction. This process is described in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 1.

B. PUBLICATION TREND OVER TIME

Of the 21 studies included in this review, the first one was published in 2014. Over the past six years, the rate of publications to quantitatively assess repeatability has increased, averaging 2.3 studies per year compared to 1.2 per year between 2014 and 2019. The peak in publication activity occurred in 2023, with a total of four studies published. The annual distribution of the included studies is presented in Figure 2. As of April 29th 2025, three studies had been published, and it remains uncertain how many additional studies assessing the repeatability of results in medical microwave imaging may be published throughout the remainder of the year.

C. DEFINITION OF CONCEPTS RELATED TO REPEATABILITY

The 21 studies included in this review quantitatively assessed repeatability; however, the terminology employed to describe this concept varied considerably. Terms such as repeatability, reproducibility, consistency, and reliability were often used interchangeably, with limited clarification of their intended

FIGURE 1. PRISMA flow diagram for the systematic literature search and review process.

FIGURE 2. Publication trend over time for studies included in the systematic review, i.e. that assess quantitatively the repeatability of their results.

meaning. Only one study provided an explicit definition: Wang et al. [11] defined reproducibility as “the degree to which repeated measurements in healthy study participants provide similar results.” The remaining studies did not provide a definition of the concept they were assessing, but rather used the terms interchangeably.

D. STUDY CHARACTERISTICS

Table 1 summarises the medical application, system characteristics, including frequency and number of antennas, and the sample size across the included studies. From the 21 studies

found in the literature, the majority ($n = 20$) focused on breast screening, while the remaining study ($n = 1$) investigated internal body temperature.

The majority of microwave systems used in the studies varied between two types: (i) ultrawideband (UWB) radar imaging systems, and (ii) transmission-based systems, each reported in nine studies. It is relevant to note that all studies using transmission-based systems originated from the same research group. Three other system types were used in the remaining three studies: (iii) narrowband radar microwave imaging, (iv) MIMO radar with magnetic nanoparticles, and (v) microwave radiometry. While microwave radiometry was used to assess internal body temperature, all other systems targeted breast screening.

Results show that of the 21 included studies, 11 assessed repeatability in human participants, 5 in physical breast phantoms only, and 5 in both volunteers and phantoms. Among the 11 studies involving human subjects, 2 were conducted on patients with breast cancer, while the remaining 9 recruited healthy volunteers. For studies employing phantoms, the sample sizes ranged from 1 to 5, with a mean of 3 and a standard deviation of 2.5. Most studies involving healthy volunteers reported sample sizes between 1 and 13 participants (mean: 4.6, SD: 4.3). One study, however, enrolled 35 participants, representing a markedly larger sample than the rest. The two studies that included breast cancer patients used sample sizes of 6 and 15.

TABLE 1. Summary of medical applications, system characteristics, and sample size across included studies. NA: Not available.

First author, Year	Application	System Type	Frequency (GHz)	No. of Antennas	Sample Size
Lavoie et al., 2018 [8]	Breast	Radar	0.01–12	1 (positionable)	Phantoms: 2 Volunteers: 3
Porter et al., 2016 [9]	Breast	Radar	2–4	16	Volunteers: 13
Smith et al., 2022 [10]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–10	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Phantoms: 1 Volunteers: 5
Wang et al., 2024 [11]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.0001–5.5	59 Tx + 240 Rx	Volunteers: 35
Porter et al., 2014 [14]	Breast	Radar	2–4	16	Volunteers: 13
Porter et al., 2014 [15]	Breast	Radar	2–4	16	Volunteers: 4
Porter et al., 2015 [16]	Breast	Radar	2–4	16	Phantoms: 1 Volunteers: 1
Ley et al., 2017 [17]	Breast	MIMO radar (magnetic nanoparticles)	0.001–2	8 Tx + 16 Rx	Volunteers: 1
Kranold et al., 2020 [18]	Breast	Radar	2–4	16	Phantoms: 2
Smith et al., 2021 [19]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–10	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Volunteers: 2
Smith et al., 2021 [20]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–10	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Patients: 6
Fortaleza et al., 2022 [21]	Breast	Narrowband	2.0125–2.100	16	Phantoms: 8
Mojabi et al., 2023 [22]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–8	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Volunteers: 1
Besler et al., 2023 [23]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–8	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Volunteers: 3
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–10	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Patients: 15
Correia et al., 2024 [25]	Breast	Radar	2–6	8	Phantoms: 2
Butterworth et al., 2025 [26]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–8	5 Tx + 5 Rx	Phantoms: 1 Volunteers: 10
Egaas et al., 2025 [27]	Internal temp.	Microwave radiometer	NA	1	Volunteers: 3
Mojabi et al., 2025 [28]	Breast	Transmission-based	0.1–8	59 Tx + 240 Rx	Phantoms: 6
Fasoula et al., 2023 [29]	Breast	Radar	0.8–4	21	Phantoms: 6
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Breast	Radar	2–4	16	Phantoms: 1 Volunteers: 1

The type of repeatability assessment varied across the included studies, as observed in Table 2. In six studies, repeatability was evaluated in both *test-retest* and *inter-session* basis. In nine studies, repeatability was evaluated using only the *inter-session* approach, involving repeated acquisitions conducted across different sessions, during which the subject or phantom was repositioned between measurements. Two more studies test repeatability of their system using a *inter-session* approach, but with the goal of comparing how the results changed in a pathological under treatment scenario, with the goal of verifying that their system is capable of detecting changes related to treatment [19], [24]. One study reported repeatability using the *inter-session* approach, and also compared the repeatability of two different microwave systems [30]. In two studies, the *test-retest* approach was used to assess repeatability, but no *inter-session* repeatability was evaluated [17], [27]. In the remaining study repeatability was reported using the *test-retest* approach, and also compared two different microwave systems [18].

The characteristics associated with the type of repeatability assessment—such as the number of sessions, measurements per session, and follow-up duration—varied considerably across the included studies. The follow-up period and number of sessions is particularly relevant for the studies evaluating *inter-session* repeatability. The follow-up time spanned from same-day acquisitions to a period of two years, with nine performing their study for more than one month. The studies that evaluated *inter-session* repeatability in the same-day performed multiple sessions in the respective day while repositioning the subject or phantom between sessions [17],

[18], [25], [26], [27]. However, a longer follow-up period did not necessarily correspond to a greater number of sessions. For example, some studies conducted daily acquisitions over defined periods—27 days in [16] and 28 days in [30]—while others performed up to four sessions distributed across two years [24]. The number of sessions varied from one to 122. For the studies that assessed *test-retest* repeatability, they commonly had only one session, where the same subjects or phantoms were measured multiple times, with the number of measurements per session ranging from 2 to 12.

E. METRICS USED IN INCLUDED STUDIES

The majority of the studies (13/21 studies) evaluated repeatability through more than one metric, with a mean of 2 metrics per study (SD: 1.0), across the 21 studies. Eighteen different metrics were identified in the included studies. Figure 3 shows each identified metric as well as the distribution of their frequency across the included studies. The most used metric is in fact the group of descriptive statistical measures (in grey in Figure 3), such as mean and standard deviation. This type of measure is normally used to establish an overall tendency and variability measurement of repeatability after the use of specific repeatability metrics. The following most used metric was the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), used in five studies. The remaining metrics were used in three or fewer studies.

Importantly, these metrics are associated to the type of input data. For example, in 9 studies the repeatability was evaluated by comparing signals. In these cases, the preferred metric was correlation-based metrics, such as

TABLE 2. Summary of repeatability assessment protocols across included studies. In cases where the inter-session assessment involved only one session, multiple measurements were conducted within the same day with repositioning to mimic inter-session conditions. NA: Not available.

First author, Year	Assessment Type	Follow-up Time	#Sessions	Times per Session
Lavoie et al., 2018 [8]	Test-retest Inter-session	[1.5, 3] months	Phantoms: 1 Volunteers: 3	Phantoms: 3 Volunteers: 1
Porter et al., 2016 [9]	Inter-session	[2, 8] months	[2, 8]	1
Smith et al., 2022 [10]	Inter-session	[4.5, 7.5] weeks	15	1
Wang et al., 2024 [11]	Test-retest Inter-session	3 weeks	3	6
Porter et al., 2014 [14]	Test-retest	8 months	[2, 6]	3
Porter et al., 2014 [15]	Inter-session	8 months	{5, 6}	1
Porter et al., 2015 [16]	Inter-session	Phantoms: 22 days Volunteers: 27 days	27	1
Ley et al., 2017 [17]	Test-retest	Same day	1	3
Kranold et al., 2020 [18]	Test-retest Inter-system	Same day	1	2
Smith et al., 2021 [19]	Inter-session	6 weeks	{14, 15}	1
Smith et al., 2021 [20]	Inter-session	6 weeks	2	1
Fortaleza et al., 2022 [21]	Longitudinal response to treatment Inter-session	5 days	5	1
Mojabi et al., 2023 [22]	Test-retest Inter-session	NA	3	3
Besler et al., 2023 [23]	Inter-session	3 weeks	3	3
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	2 years	[2, 4]	1
Correia et al., 2024 [25]	Test-retest Inter-session	Same day	1	Test-retest: 10 Inter-session: 3
Butterworth et al., 2025 [26]	Inter-session	Same day	1	Phantoms: 12 Volunteers: 3
Egaas et al., 2025 [27]	Test-retest	Same day	1	4
Mojabi et al., 2025 [28]	Inter-session	4 months	122	1
Fasoula et al., 2023 [29]	Test-retest Inter-session	5 days	4	2
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Inter-session Inter-system	28 days	28	1

FIGURE 3. Distribution of the number of times each metric was used across the included studies. SSIM: Structural Similarity Index, MHD: Modified Hausdorff Distance, NRMSE: Normalised Root Mean Squared Error, SEM: Standard Error Measurement, ICC: Intraclass Correlation Coefficient, CV: Coefficient of variation.

cross-correlation and Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) (6/9 studies). Image-based metrics were used in 18 studies, with SSIM being the most used (5/18 studies).

The metrics employed across the included studies were organised into five thematic groups according to the

context that they were used to assess repeatability: spatial consistency, visual and structural similarity, signal pattern similarity, performance summary metrics, and statistical-based. This categorisation was derived empirically following full-text analysis of each study. The groups are described below, together with the mathematical definitions of the corresponding figures of merit reported in the included studies, where A and B represent two sets of points, with $|A|$ and $|B|$ being the number of points in each set, respectively.

1) SPATIAL CONSISTENCY

Spatial consistency metrics are designed to examine the degree to which two datasets remain spatially aligned across repeated scans. Commonly used approaches include distance-based metrics, which compute point-wise dissimilarities between sets, and overlap-based metrics, which quantify the degree of shared area or volume. Among the distance-based approaches, the Euclidean distance, the Modified Hausdorff Distance (MHD) [31], and Fréchet distance [32] were the three figures of merit used. Lavoie et al. [8] computed the Euclidean distance between the locations of maximum intensity values in two images. This metric is denoted as:

$$\text{Euclidean dist}_{\text{MaxResponse}}(A, B) = \|a_{\text{max}} - b_{\text{max}}\|, \quad (1)$$

with a_{max} and b_{max} being the coordinates of the maximum response locations in the images.

MHD computes the average spatial distance between two objects, being used to compare image outlines, and is defined as:

$$\text{MHD}(A, B) = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{a \in A} \min_{b \in B} \|a - b\|, \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{b \in B} \min_{a \in A} \|b - a\| \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where $\|a - b\|$ is the ℓ_2 norm (i.e. Euclidean distance) between points a and b . This metric was used in two studies [8], [26]. Lavoie et al. [8] defined two uses of MHD: MHD-outline, which compares the surfaces of reconstructed volumes, and MHD-response, which computes the MHD between regions exceeding a defined intensity threshold. Butterworth et al. [26] used MHD to compute the spatial alignment between point clouds of the breast volume. In addition, Butterworth et al. applied the Fréchet distance between the surfaces of the point clouds, as an alternative to MHD. This metric determines the similarity between two sets while accounting for the order of points along curves or meshes and is typically recommended when comparing continuous shapes such as anatomical contours. The Fréchet distance is defined as:

$$F(A, B) = \inf_{\alpha, \beta} \max_{t \in [0, 1]} \left\{ d(A(\alpha(t)), B(\beta(t))) \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where α and β are reparameterisations of A and B between 0 and 1, t is the step between each triangle in the mesh, and d is the distance between the points at parameter t . MHD and Fréchet distance return a value of zero when the shapes are identical and increase with spatial divergence, without imposing an upper limit.

In terms of overlap-based metrics, the Dice coefficient [33] was one of the measures to quantify overlap between two sets:

$$\text{Dice coefficient}(A, B) = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|}. \quad (4)$$

This metric ranges from 0 (no overlap) to 1 (perfect overlap) and was employed in a single study by Butterworth et al. [26].

Another reported overlap-based metric is the volume-mismatch metric, which quantifies the proportion of non-overlapping volume between two sets:

$$\text{Volume mismatch}(A, B) = \frac{|A \cup B| - |A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}. \quad (5)$$

A value of 0 indicates complete overlap, while 1 corresponds to no overlap. Lavoie et al. [8] used this metric to quantify shape differences of the breast in full 3D reconstructions between repeated acquisitions.

2) VISUAL AND STRUCTURAL SIMILARITY

In the context of repeatability assessment in MMWI, visual and structural similarity metrics provide insight into how consistent image features remain across repeated acquisitions.

Rather than focusing on spatial displacement or exact geometric correspondence, these approaches evaluate similarity based on local image features or intensity patterns. SSIM [34] was designed to quantify the degree of resemblance between two sets of points or images by analysing the relationships of pixels that are spatially near each other, and was originally motivated to reflect perceived image quality as judged by the human visual system. It compares local statistics of luminance (i.e., brightness), contrast (i.e., dynamic range), and structure (i.e., patterns and textures in the image), which are then aggregated to produce a global similarity score. In the most general formula of SSIM, parameters that define the relative importance of luminance, contrast, and structure can be set. The following equation represents a widely spread simplified version of SSIM in which the importance of each parameter is equal:

$$\text{SSIM}(A, B) = \frac{(2\mu_A\mu_B + C1)(2\sigma_{AB} + C2)}{(\mu_A^2 + \mu_B^2 + C1)(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2 + C2)}, \quad (6)$$

where μ_A and μ_B are the mean intensities of the two images, σ_A and σ_B are the standard deviations of the intensity, σ_{AB} is the covariance between the two images, and $C1$ and $C2$ are constants that stabilise the division. SSIM is 1 when comparing identical images, but its minimum value depends on specific image content and can even be negative in some cases. SSIM was used in five studies [8], [9], [14], [16], [30] to evaluate repeatability.

Another metric used to assess visual similarity was the 2D Pearson correlation coefficient (2PCC), which quantifies the linear relationship between two images. It was used by Smith et al. [10] to evaluate the similarity of the generated images across different sessions by comparing each image to the average image. The 2PCC is defined as:

$$2\text{PCC}(A, B) = \frac{\sum_{i,j} (a_{ij} - \bar{a})(b_{ij} - \bar{b})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i,j} (a_{ij} - \bar{a})^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i,j} (b_{ij} - \bar{b})^2}}, \quad (7)$$

where a_{ij} and b_{ij} are the pixel values at position (i, j) in images A and B , respectively, and \bar{a} and \bar{b} are the mean pixel values of images A and B . The 2PCC ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect positive linear relationship, -1 indicates a perfect negative linear relationship, and 0 indicates no linear relationship.

Difference-based metrics, such as Root-Mean-Square Error (RMSE), compute the magnitude of pixel-wise discrepancies between images. RMSE provides a measure of the average magnitude of the differences between two sets of points:

$$\text{RMSE}(A, B) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (A - B)^2}, \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of points in sets A and B . RMSE is always non-negative, with lower values indicating better agreement between the sets. RMSE is commonly normalised

to facilitate the comparison of results across different scales or units. Normalised RMSE (NRMSE) is defined in [8] as:

$$\text{NRMSE}(A, B) = \frac{\text{RMSE}(A, B)}{\Delta_{\min}}, \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta_{\min} = \min(\max(A) - \min(A), \max(B) - \min(B))$. The NRMSE ranges from zero to one, where zero indicates no difference and one indicates maximum difference, thus representing the average error per voxel. Lavoie et al. [8] used NRMSE and compared it with SSIM.

In three studies [9], [14], [15], the peak pixel intensity was employed as a metric to evaluate repeatability. In [14] and [15], the authors assessed the consistency of the strongest response across sessions by comparing the maximum pixel intensities of two reconstructed images. Specifically, they computed a difference image by subtracting the pixel intensities of the first scan from those of the second. The peak value of this difference image was then analysed relative to the peaks of the original images. The peak difference was compared between scan pairs, with images obtained at different time points providing a proxy for the repeatability of the measurements over time. The study by Porter et al. [9] used a different approach to evaluate the peak pixel intensities across multiple repeated scans. Differential images were formed using the first scan as a calibration baseline, and each image was normalised to the peak intensity of the reference image.

3) SIGNAL PATTERN SIMILARITY

Part of the included studies reported metrics that quantify signal pattern similarity. These approaches do not rely on spatial correspondence, but rather on the degree to which signal traces remain consistent across different sessions. One simple hypothesis is to subtract two signals acquired at different time points; a larger difference between them would mean a lower similarity. This approach was used in two studies [18], [27].

Two other commonly used measures in this context are the PCC in 1D and cross-correlation. In the studies reporting these metrics, the signal obtained during each subsequent acquisition for a given antenna was compared against a baseline signal—typically the first scan acquired—to assess repeatability.

As it was defined for the 2PCC in 2D, the PCC in 1D is defined as:

$$\text{PCC}(X, Y) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}, \quad (10)$$

where n is the number of points in the signals X and Y , \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the means of the sets X and Y , respectively. PCC was used in three studies to evaluate similarity between aligned signals [10], [19], [20].

Cross-correlation generalises the concept of PCC to measure the similarity as a function of a temporal or spatial shift between two signals. This metric is robust to phase shift or time alignment discrepancies that may occur between

repeated acquisitions. Cross-correlation was used in three studies to assess the similarity of signal patterns over time [9], [14], [16].

4) PERFORMANCE SUMMARY METRICS

In contrast to studies that employed explicit metrics to evaluate repeatability, three studies instead reported performance metrics commonly used to characterise the quality of reconstructed images in microwave imaging systems. Ley et al. [17] determined the full width at half maximum (FWHM; measures the extent of the detection), and the crosstalk to noise ratio (CNR; ratio between the mean amplitude of the crosstalk signal and the background system noise) for the signals acquired to assess repeatability of their system. Kranold et al. [18], and Correia et al. [25] computed the signal to clutter ratio (SCR; contrast between the target response and background), signal to mean ratio (SMR; target strength relative to average image intensity), and localisation error (LE; deviation between actual and reconstructed target position) of the reconstructed images by their system. Such metrics summarise key aspects of system performance—namely, the capacity to detect and localise targets—which may indirectly reflect repeatability when the same targets are consistently present across repeated acquisitions.

5) STATISTICAL-BASED METRICS

While the metrics discussed in previous sections focus primarily on pairwise comparisons between repeated images or signal acquisitions, statistical-based measures offer a complementary perspective by evaluating how such metrics vary across multiple time points or sessions. These approaches quantify the overall consistency of repeated measurements, often across different subjects or conditions. Simple statistical descriptors such as the mean, median, SD, and range were used to summarise the central tendency and variability of measurements [10], [18], [19], [20], [21], [23], [24], [28], [30]. For instance, after evaluating the repeatability between their acquisitions pairwise Porter et al. [30] computed the mean, SD and range of the values to quantify the overall repeatability of their results across all acquisitions. A series of studies from the same research group [10], [19], [20], [23], [24], [28], all employing variations of the same microwave imaging prototype, reported descriptive statistics of the average permittivity values within the reconstructed images. In these systems, each image pixel represents the relative permittivity of the tissue at the corresponding location. By quantifying the variability in average permittivity values across repeated scans using basic summary statistics, these studies aimed to evaluate the stability and repeatability of the imaging output over time.

Additionally, Smith et al. [24] conducted a *post hoc* two-way ANOVA on the average permittivity values of the scans to investigate whether changes observed between baseline and six-week follow-up scans were statistically significant across all volunteers.

A separate group of statistical metrics was used in one study to assess the global repeatability of microwave imaging outcomes. Wang et al. [11] employed the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC), the standard error of measurement (SEM), and the coefficient of variation (CV), calculated based on the average relative permittivity of each reconstructed image. ICC was used to assess the proportion of measurement variance related to inter-subject differences. The ICC quantifies the consistency or agreement between repeated measurements by decomposing the total variability into within-subject and between-subject components. In a one-way random-effects model [35], the ICC is given by:

$$\text{ICC} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{between}}^2}{\sigma_{\text{between}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{within}}^2}, \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{between}}^2$ and σ_{within}^2 denote the between-subject and within-subject variance, respectively. ICC values range from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (perfect agreement). ICC can accommodate multiple sources of variability across repeated measurements and is therefore well-suited to study designs involving repeated imaging sessions of the same subjects.

The SEM quantifies the absolute measurement error and is derived from the within-subject variability:

$$\text{SEM} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{within}}^2}. \quad (12)$$

Finally, CV was reported to express measurement variability relative to the mean:

$$\%CV = \frac{\sigma_{\text{Total}}}{\bar{\mu}} \times 100\%, \quad (13)$$

where, $\bar{\mu}$ is the mean value.

F. REPORTED REPEATABILITY METRICS

Tables 3, 4, 5, and 6 summarise the repeatability metrics and their respective values reported across the 21 studies included in this review. These tables focus on signal pattern similarity metrics, spatial consistency metrics, visual and structural similarity metrics, and performance summary or statistical-based metrics, respectively.

Despite variability in the reported metrics, the majority of studies consistently demonstrated high repeatability, with exception of Butterworth et al. [26], with relatively lower repeatability values. Among signal metrics used in multiple studies, cross-correlation and PCC were the most frequent. Cross-correlation ranged from 0.592 to 0.999 across the three studies employing it, while PCC varied between 0.86 and 1.0 in the three studies that reported it.

Regarding image-based metrics, the SSIM ranged from 0.41 to 1.0 across four of the five studies that reported it. However, in the study by Lavoie et al. [8], SSIM was varied in the range 0.18 to 0.38. The NRMSE was reported in two studies [8], [29], with values between 0.02 and 0.24. Notably, the Fréchet distance—reported only by Butterworth et al. [26]—showed relatively large values (i.e. lower repeatability), even in phantom-based assessments.

Three studies employed both signal and image-based metrics [9], [10], [14]. Two of these studies [9], [10] obtained better metric values when considering signal-based metrics, as aligned with the general trend found, and with a broader variability of values for the image-based metrics. In contrast, Porter et al. [14] reported worse values for signal cross-correlation than for SSIM values, with a narrower range of values obtained for the image-based metrics.

Among the six studies that assessed both *test-retest* and *inter-session* repeatability, five showed higher repeatability for the *test-retest* condition across all reported metrics [8], [14], [22], [25], [29]. Wang et al. [11] was the only exception, with comparable metric values between the two assessment types.

In studies evaluating repeatability with phantoms and human participants under the same repeatability condition, phantoms consistently yielded higher repeatability values [10], [14], [16], [26]. Lavoie et al. [8] was excluded from this comparison, as phantoms and volunteers were used in different assessment types, with phantoms used to assess *test-retest* repeatability and human subjects *inter-session* repeatability.

G. REPORTED SOURCES OF VARIABILITY

In 14 of the included studies, the authors reported factors that may have affected the repeatability of their results. Figure 4 illustrates these sources of variability, with each block representing a distinct source and annotated with the studies that identified it. At the bottom of the diagram, the studies that did not report any variability factors are also listed.

The most frequently reported sources of variability were subject-related. The most cited factor, reported in seven studies, was volunteer or phantom repositioning between sessions [8], [9], [10], [11], [14], [17], [21]. The second most frequent factor, reported in six studies, was the difficulty in imaging breasts of smaller size [9], [11], [15], [23], [26], [28].

Hardware-related changes, such as variations in electronic noise or scanner performance over time, were identified in three studies [8], [11], [25]. Tissue-related variability, including physiological changes due to the menstrual cycle [9], [16] or pathological differences between healthy and diseased tissue [20], was also reported.

In two studies, internal repositioning of breast tissue, such as glandular tissue, was specifically reported as a factor affecting repeatability, even when external positioning remained consistent [10], [26].

Additional individual factors reported by single studies include scan misalignment [8], changes in coupling medium [14], signal interference [21], and operator interference [25].

IV. DISCUSSION

This systematic review comprehensively examined how repeatability has been quantitatively evaluated in MMWI systems, including the protocols used, and the repeatability

TABLE 3. Summary of assessment type and signal-based similarity metrics across included studies. PCC: Pearson Correlation Coefficient. NA: Not available.

First author, Year	Assessment Type	Cross-correlation	PCC	Signal difference
Lavoie et al., 2018 [8]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2016 [9]	Inter-session	[0.76, 0.99]	—	—
Smith et al., 2022 [10]	Inter-session	—	Phantoms: [0.98, 1]; Volunteers: [0.79, 1]	—
Wang et al., 2024 [11]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2014 [14]	Test-retest	Test-retest: [0.882, 0.999];	—	—
Porter et al., 2014 [15]	Inter-session	Inter-session: [0.592, 0.999]	—	—
Porter et al., 2015 [16]	Inter-session	—	Phantoms: mean = 0.995; Volunteers: mean = 0.990	—
Ley et al., 2017 [17]	Test-retest	—	—	—
Kranold et al., 2020 [18]	Test-retest Inter-system	—	—	Table-based: Test-retest: mean = 0.0002 (SD = 0.0003), CI[95%] = [0.0001, 0.0002]; Wearable: Test-retest: mean = 0.0003 (SD = 0.0010), CI[95%] = [0.0002, 0.0004]
Smith et al., 2021 [19]	Inter-session	—	[0.86, 0.99]	—
Smith et al., 2021 [20]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	—	Healthy: [0.968, 0.984]; Treated: [0.95, 0.992]	—
Fortaleza et al., 2022 [21]	Inter-session	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2023 [22]	Test-retest	—	—	—
Besler et al., 2023 [23]	Inter-session	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—
Correia et al., 2024 [25]	Test-retest	—	—	—
Butterworth et al., 2025 [26]	Inter-session	—	—	—
Egaas et al., 2025 [27]	Test-retest	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2025 [28]	Inter-session	—	—	—
Fasoula et al., 2023 [29]	Test-retest	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Inter-session Test-retest Inter-system	—	—	—

Studies that did not report sources of variability: [16], [17], [20], [22], [25], [27], [28]

FIGURE 4. Sources of variability affecting the repeatability of MMWI prototypes, as reported by the included studies. Each box represents a distinct source of variability and lists the studies that identified it.

achieved in each study. Systems with elevated repeatability present consistent results under equivalent conditions, being

capable of capture clinically relevant changes in targeted tissues. Among the selected 21 studies, the first study found to quantitatively evaluate the repeatability of their MMWI system was published in 2014 [14]. Remarkably, 20 out of the 21 studies were focused on breast health applications, and only one addressed a different clinical domain - internal body temperature measurement. When placed in a broader context of the MMWI literature for breast health, which comprised 935 studies in Scopus on the 12th August 2025 and published since 2014, this number is strikingly low representing only 2.14% of all papers. This underscores the limited attention this critical concept has received, as seen in the Results section.

Different types of systems had their repeatability evaluated across the MMWI literature, but the majority focused on UWB radar, with no study focused on microwave tomography. Among the included studies, the systems were reported to exhibit repeatability under the tested conditions. However, multiple metrics were reported. Some metrics, such as PCC, cross-correlation, and the SSIM, were more

TABLE 4. Summary of spatial consistency metrics reported across included studies. MHD: Modified Hausdorff Distance. NA: Not available.

First author, Year	Assessment Type	Euclidean distance	MHD	Fréchet distance	Dice Coefficient	Volume mismatch
Lavoie et al., 2018 [8]	Test-retest Inter-session	Test-retest: [0, 4] mm; Inter-session: [4, 44] mm	Test-retest: MHD-outline: [0.3, 0.5] mm; MHD-response: [0, 4] mm; Inter-session: MHD-outline: [1.5, 3.5] mm; MHD-response: [7, 58] mm	—	—	Test-retest: [2, 2.5] %; Inter-session: [9, 32] %
Porter et al., 2016 [9]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2022 [10]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Wang et al., 2024 [11]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2014 [14]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2014 [15]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2015 [16]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Ley et al., 2017 [17]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—	—
Kranold et al., 2020 [18]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2021 [19]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2021 [20]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—	—	—
Fortaleza et al., 2022 [21]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2023 [22]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—	—
Besler et al., 2023 [23]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—	—	—
Correia et al., 2024 [25]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Butterworth et al., 2025 [26]	Inter-session	—	Phantoms: median = 3.4 mm Volunteers: median = 4.4 mm	Phantoms: mean = 11 cm Volunteers: [1, 12.5] cm	Phantoms: mean = 0.91 Volunteers: mean = 0.74	—
Egaas et al., 2025 [27]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2025 [28]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Fasoula et al., 2023 [29]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Inter-session Inter-system	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE 5. Summary of visual and structural similarity metrics across included studies. SSIM: Structural Similarity Index Measure; NRMSE: Normalized Root Mean Squared Error. NA: Not available.

First author, Year	Assessment Type	SSIM	2D PCC	NRMSE	Max Pixel Intensity
Lavoie et al., 2018 [8]	Test-retest Inter-session	Test-retest: [0.6, 0.9]; Inter-session: [0.18, 0.38]	—	Test-retest: [0.02, 0.04]; Inter-session: [0.08, 0.24]	—
Porter et al., 2016 [9]	Inter-session	[0.41, 0.79]	—	—	mean = 8.59 (SD = 10.3) dB
Smith et al., 2022 [10]	Inter-session	—	[0.55, 0.99]	—	—
Wang et al., 2024 [11]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2014 [14]	Test-retest	Test-retest: [0.85, 1];	—	—	Test-retest: [-46, -22.7] dB;
Porter et al., 2014 [15]	Inter-session	Inter-session: [0.77, 0.99]	—	—	Inter-session: [-44, -16.8] dB
Porter et al., 2015 [16]	Inter-session	Phantom: [0.98, 0.99]; Volunteer: [0.64, 0.97]	—	—	mean = -13.69 dB
Ley et al., 2017 [17]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Kranold et al., 2020 [18]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2021 [19]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2021 [20]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—	—
Fortaleza et al., 2022 [21]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2023 [22]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Besler et al., 2023 [23]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Inter-session Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—	—
Correia et al., 2024 [25]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Butterworth et al., 2025 [26]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Egaas et al., 2025 [27]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2025 [28]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Fasoula et al., 2023 [29]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	—	Test-retest: mean = 0.061 (SD = 0.058); Inter-session: mean = 0.196 (SD = 0.117)	—
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Test-retest Inter-system	Wearable: Phantoms: mean = 0.960 (SD = 0.022); Volunteers: mean = 0.925 (SD = 0.019); Table-based: Phantoms: mean = 0.992 (SD = 0.005); Volunteers: mean = 0.869 (SD = 0.101)	—	—	—

TABLE 6. Summary of performance summary metrics and statistical-based metrics across included studies. ICC: Intraclass Correlation Coefficient; SEM: Standard Error of Measurement; CV: Coefficient of Variation.

First author, Year	Assessment Type	Performance metrics	ICC	SEM	% CV
Lavoie et al., 2018 [8]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2016 [9]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2022 [10]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Wang et al., 2024 [11]	Test-retest Inter-session	—	Test-retest: 0.92 CI[95%]=[0.86, 0.96]; Inter-session: 0.92 CI[95%]=[0.87, 0.96]	Test-retest: 1.50; Inter-session: 1.51	Test-retest: 5.17; Inter-session: 5.39
Porter et al., 2014 [14]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2014 [15]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2015 [16]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Ley et al., 2017 [17]	Test-retest	FWHM = [102, 160] ps; CNR = [54, 79] dB	—	—	—
Kranold et al., 2020 [18]	Test-retest Inter-system	Table-based: SCR = 1.4 dB, SMR = 45.5 dB, LE = 2.0 cm; Wearable: SCR = 1.3 dB, SMR = 30.4 dB, LE = 1.2 cm	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2021 [19]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2021 [20]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Fortaleza et al., 2022 [21]	Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2023 [22]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Besler et al., 2023 [23]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Smith et al., 2023 [24]	Longitudinal response to treatment	—	—	—	—
Correia et al., 2024 [25]	Test-retest Inter-session	Test-retest: SCR = {2.28, 2.32} dB, SMR = {10.85, 10.77} dB, LE = {1.4, 2.0} cm; Inter-session: SCR = {2.73, 1.02, 2.28} dB, SMR = {10.46, 8.55, 10.85} dB, LE = {4.5, 2.2, 1.4} cm	—	—	—
Butterworth et al., 2025 [26]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Egaas et al., 2025 [27]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Mojabi et al., 2025 [28]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Fasoula et al., 2023 [29]	Test-retest	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Inter-session	—	—	—	—
Porter et al., 2016 [30]	Inter-system	—	—	—	—

frequently applied, while others—such as Fréchet distance—were reported only once.

As expected, *test-retest* evaluations tended to yield higher repeatability values than *inter-session* assessments, given the greater variability introduced by longer time intervals and subject repositioning. Similarly, studies conducted on phantoms generally reported higher repeatability values than those involving human participants. This difference can be attributed to the absence of biological variability and the more consistent positioning achievable under controlled phantom conditions. In MMWI literature, repeatability was evaluated both at the signal and image levels, which cannot be compared directly. However, in general the reported repeatability was higher for signal-based metrics than for the image-based metrics. Specifically, two of the three studies that reported repeatability for the two domains had higher and less variable values of repeatability metrics at the signal level, although further evidence is needed. Nonetheless, this observation is potentially associated to additional variability introduced during image reconstruction. While signal-level metrics reflect measurements closer to the raw acquisition, image-level metrics integrate multiple processing steps where small inconsistencies may be magnified. The relative contribution of these factors remains unclear and requires further investigation.

A key observation from this review is the substantial methodological heterogeneity across studies. As discussed, the metrics used, type of assessment conducted, and

repeatability of signal or images varied significantly between studies. Additionally, the number of sessions, times per session and follow-up times differed considerably. While *test-retest* protocols were relatively consistent, *inter-session* assessments varied from same-day repositioning to follow-up times of weeks, months, or even a year.

Metric selection and reporting practices varied substantially across the included studies. While some employed multiple metrics, others relied on a single quantitative measure. As discussed earlier, each metric captures distinct characteristics of the underlying data, which allowed us to empirically classify the reported metrics into five groups.

Signal-based metrics are important to evaluate repeatability in systems where an image is not reconstructed, such as sensing systems. In systems that do reconstruct images, repeatability can be assessed using both signal- and image-based metrics; however, our findings revealed that repeatability metrics derived from images consistently yielded lower and more variable values than those based on signals. Ultimately, image-level assessment should be prioritised, as the clinical utility of MMWI prototypes depends on the repeatability of the reconstructed image rather than the underlying signal. In this context, the goal is twofold: to ensure that spatial and morphological features (e.g., glandular patterns) are preserved and that voxel intensities remain stable across acquisitions.

As observed in Figure 5, SSIM demonstrates the strongest capacity to evaluate both aspects simultaneously compared

FIGURE 5. Perceptual map of image-based repeatability metrics reported in the included studies. The x-axis represents the ability of a metric to capture spatial fidelity, while the y-axis represents its ability to capture intensity stability. Metrics positioned higher and further to the right are more comprehensive in assessing repeatability between images. The red cross represents the ideal metric. SSIM: Structural Similarity Index, MHD: Modified Hausdorff Distance, NRMSE: Normalised Root Mean Squared Error, 2PCC: 2D Pearson Correlation Coefficient.

with the other metrics. SSIM is probably the most popular metric to evaluate image quality assessment in medical images. However, limitations have been reported that hinder its application in medical imaging, including underestimation of distortion near hard edges, instability in regions of low variance, and insensitivity to variations in high-intensity areas, which limits their effectiveness to capture structure changes [36]. While it captures structure better than intensity-only metrics, it is less robust than spatial consistency metrics such as MHD or Dice Coefficient. A more comprehensive approach could therefore involve combining metrics from different groups—for example, pairing a measure of spatial consistency with SSIM. One study (Lavoie et al. [8]) adopted this approach.

Performance summary metrics were also used to assess repeatability in three studies. They are important to assess the capacity of the developed systems to detect and localise targets. However, these do not directly quantify repeatability and should therefore be reported together with, rather than in place of, metrics that explicitly capture repeatability. Statistical-based metrics can reflect the overall repeatability of one prototype. Simple descriptive measures, such as the mean, median, SD and range are capable of informing the central tendency and the variability associated with the various acquisitions. An example is the study by Fasoula et al. [29] that reported the mean and SD of the NRMSE across acquisitions. More complex statistical measures, such as the ICC, can provide a more robust quantification of repeatability by accounting for both within-subject and between-subject variability. However,

only one study [11] reported ICC. The ICC is particularly valuable as it quantifies the proportion of total variance attributable to true differences between subjects versus measurement error. High ICC values indicate that most variability arises from actual differences rather than inconsistencies in measurement. ICC can even be used to assess the repeatability of different metrics, such as the NRMSE and SSIM, instead of reporting their mean and SD, as ICC quantifies the consistency of the metric.

In this review, potential sources of variability affecting the repeatability of MMWI prototypes were identified across 14 studies. The most frequently reported factors were related to phantom or patient repositioning between sessions and difficulties in imaging small breasts. Additional sources of variability were noted, some of which are common to all MMWI systems—such as hardware changes—while others are device-specific, including changes in the coupling medium or repositioning of tissue within the breast. For example, two studies [10], [26] from the same research group, working with a transmission-based system in which the breast is slightly compressed between two arrays, reported translational repositioning of breast tissue within the breast, which is associated with this specific device. In this way, some sources of variability can be mitigated through specific design or procedural adaptations. It is, however, important to note that reporting of factors affecting repeatability was inconsistent in the 21 selected papers, and one third of the studies included did not provide such discussion.

One of the most striking limitations of the literature to date is its narrow clinical scope, with almost all repeatability assessments focused on breast applications. Also to note that no study evaluated repeatability for microwave tomography systems, leaving a gap in understanding for this imaging modality. Sample sizes were often small, and phantom-based results, while encouraging, may overestimate repeatability in real-world scenarios. The heterogeneity in study design, protocols, and the lack of standardised outcome measures reduces comparability. This diversity not only complicates comparison but also limits the ability to aggregate findings quantitatively. In addition, the underreporting of variability sources hinders the identification of key technical or procedural factors that influence measurement stability.

This review also has inherent limitations. Although a comprehensive search strategy was applied across multiple databases, it is possible that relevant studies published outside indexed journals, in other languages, or under alternative terminology were not captured. Additionally, the review did not conduct a formal meta-analysis due to the substantial heterogeneity in study designs, protocols, and outcome measures, meaning that conclusions are necessarily qualitative. Metrics were classified into functional groups *post hoc*, based on a thematic analysis of their mathematical definitions and typical applications. While alternative categorisations are possible, no comparable classification has, to the authors' knowledge, been previously reported. Nonetheless, these methodological choices reflect the current state of the

literature and were necessary to enable synthesis across highly variable studies.

A. RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings emphasise that repeatability assessment is not systematically performed. It must become a routine and a standardised component of system validation before clinical integration can be achieved. Future work should focus on harmonising protocols for repeatability assessment, encompassing both *test-retest* and *inter-session* designs, with *inter-session* evaluations conducted over clinically relevant time intervals (i.e. days to months) rather than same-day repositioning alone. Protocols should specify the number of sessions, acquisitions per session, and follow-up periods, and should be designed to ensure statistical robustness while recognising the logistical constraints of clinical trials. Repeatability evaluation should ideally begin with phantoms to establish a baseline system stability, followed by human studies to capture biological and procedural variability. For systems producing reconstructed images, spatial consistency metrics should be used alongside SSIM. Central tendency and variation measures (e.g., mean and standard deviation) of the metrics should be reported as a global assessment of repeatability across acquisitions, sessions, and subjects; ICC may also be employed instead to give an overall repeatability value. Such an approach enables comprehensive assessment and facilitates cross-study comparison. Common sources of variability—such as repositioning, tissue differences, and breast size—should be reported and their impact considered. Finally, repeatability assessment should be expanded beyond breast imaging and include other MMWI applications, as well as to microwave tomography systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This systematic review examined the current state of repeatability assessment in MMWI systems, revealing its limited implementation and substantial methodological heterogeneity. While most studies reported acceptable repeatability, the diversity in protocols and metrics hinders cross-study comparison. Key sources of variability, such as repositioning and tissue differences, were inconsistently reported. To advance the field, standardised protocols encompassing both *test-retest* and *inter-session* designs are needed, along with harmonised metric selection that captures both spatial and intensity fidelity. Ultimately, the adoption of comprehensive repeatability assessment will facilitate the clinical translation of MMWI systems across a range of applications, beyond breast imaging, and support the broader development of consistent imaging systems.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data used in this systematic review are derived from publicly available peer-reviewed journal articles available through the following databases: Scopus, IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, and PubMed. The full list of included studies and their respective references is already reported.

For transparency and reproducibility, all search strategies and inclusion criteria are provided in the supplementary material. The PRISMA checklist is also included in the supplementary material. A protocol for this systematic review was prepared and can be made available upon request.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Fasoula, L. Duchesne, J. D. Gil Cano, B. M. Moloney, S. M. Abd Elwahab, and M. J. Kerin, "Automated breast lesion detection and characterization with the wavelia microwave breast imaging system: Methodological proof-of-concept on first-in-human patient data," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 21, p. 9998, Oct. 2021.
- [2] A. Janjic, I. Akduman, M. Cayoren, O. Bugdayci, and M. E. Aribal, "Microwave breast lesion classification-results from clinical investigation of the SAFE microwave breast cancer system," *Academic Radiol.*, vol. 30, pp. S1–S8, Sep. 2023.
- [3] M. Shere, I. Lyburn, R. Sidebottom, H. Massey, C. Gillett, and L. Jones, "MARIA m5: A multicentre clinical study to evaluate the ability of the micrima radio-wave radar breast imaging system (MARIA) to detect lesions in the symptomatic breast," *Eur. J. Radiol.*, vol. 116, pp. 61–67, Jul. 2019.
- [4] L. Sani, A. Vispa, R. Loretoni, M. Duranti, N. Ghavami, D. A. Sánchez-Bayuela, S. Caschera, M. Paoli, A. Bigotti, M. Badia, M. Scorsipa, G. Raspa, M. Ghavami, and G. Tiberi, "Breast lesion detection through MammoWave device: Empirical detection capability assessment of microwave images' parameters," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 16, no. 4, Apr. 2021, Art. no. e0250005.
- [5] H. X. Barnhart and D. P. Barboriak, "Applications of the repeatability of quantitative imaging biomarkers: A review of statistical analysis of repeat data sets," *Translational Oncol.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 231–235, Dec. 2009.
- [6] M. J. Page et al., "The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews," *BMJ*, vol. 372, p. n71, Mar. 2021.
- [7] M. Ouzzani, H. Hammady, Z. Fedorowicz, and A. Elmagarmid, "Rayyan—A web and mobile app for systematic reviews," *Systematic Rev.*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 210, Dec. 2016.
- [8] B. R. Lavoie, J. Bourqui, E. C. Fear, and M. Okoniewski, "Metrics for assessing the similarity of microwave breast imaging scans of healthy volunteers," *IEEE Trans. Med. Imag.*, vol. 37, no. 8, pp. 1788–1798, Aug. 2018.
- [9] E. Porter, M. Coates, and M. Popovic, "An early clinical study of time-domain microwave radar for breast health monitoring," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 530–539, Mar. 2016.
- [10] K. Smith, J. Bourqui, D. Garrett, S. Zarnke, M. Owjimehr, D. Deutscher, T. Fung, and E. Fear, "Microwave imaging of the breast: Consistency of measurements over time," *IEEE J. Electromagn., RF Microw. Med. Biol.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 61–67, Mar. 2022.
- [11] Z. Wang, P. Mojabi, S. Price, Z. Lasemiimemi, B. Besler, J. Bourqui, D. Deutscher, B. Besler, H. Shen, B. Docktor, R. Y. Tsang, and E. Fear, "Reproducibility of microwave breast imaging: Analysis of regular scans of a group of volunteers," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 1–10, May 2025.
- [12] A. Fasoula and L. Duchesne, "The Wavelia#2 microwave breast imaging scanner: Experimental performance analysis towards clinical investigation," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Antennas Propag. USNC-URSI Radio Sci. Meeting (USNC-URSI)*, Jul. 2023, pp. 305–306.
- [13] L. Duchesne, G. Papatrechas, A. Raveneau, and A. Fasoula, "Improvement of the multifactorial stability of the Wavelia#2 microwave breast imaging scanner: Towards enhanced scan repeatability performance," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Antennas Propag. INC/USNC-URSI Radio Sci. Meeting (AP-S/INC-USNC-URSI)*, Jul. 2024, pp. 1515–1516.
- [14] E. Porter, A. Santorelli, and M. Popovic, "Time-domain microwave radar applied to breast imaging: Measurement reliability in a clinical setting," *Prog. Electromagn. Res.*, vol. 149, pp. 119–132, 2014.
- [15] E. Porter, A. Santorelli, M. Coates, and M. Popovic, "Breast tissue screening with microwave time-domain radar: Initial clinical trials," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Antenna Meas. Appl. (CAMA)*, Nov. 2014, pp. 1–4.
- [16] E. Porter, A. Santorelli, R. Kazemi, and M. Popovic, "Microwave time-domain radar: Healthy tissue variations over the menstrual cycle," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 14, pp. 1310–1313, 2015.

- [17] S. Ley, M. Helbig, J. Sachs, B. Faenger, and I. Hilger, "Investigations of signal reproducibility and influences of vital signs for microwave breast cancer imaging: An initial volunteer trial," in *IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Symp. Dig.*, May 2017, pp. 1–4.
- [18] L. Kranold, M. Ozmen, M. Coates, and M. Popovic, "Microwave radar for breast health monitoring: System performance protocol," in *IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Symp. Dig.*, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–3.
- [19] K. Smith, B. C. Besler, and E. Fear, "Data-adaptive filtering approach for microwave breast imaging: Consistency of volunteer scans," in *Proc. IEEE 19th Int. Symp. Antenna Technol. Appl. Electromagn. (ANTEM)*, Aug. 2021, pp. 1–2.
- [20] K. Smith, J. Bourqui, P. Grendarova, M. Lesiuk, S. Quirk, M. Roumeliotis, and E. Fear, "Microwave imaging for monitoring patients post-radiation treatment: An initial investigation," in *Proc. 15th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Mar. 2021, pp. 1–4.
- [21] L. Fortaleza and M. Popovic, "Narrowband microwave breast screening: Repeatability study with phantoms," *IEEE J. Electromagn., RF Microw. Med. Biol.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 260–266, Jun. 2022.
- [22] P. Mojabi, J. Bourqui, B. A. Besler, B. Docktor, and E. Fear, "Point-of-care microwave scanner for monitoring breast cancer treatment: An initial stability analysis," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Antennas Propag. USNC-URSI Radio Sci. Meeting (USNC-URSI)*, Jul. 2023, pp. 309–310.
- [23] B. C. Besler, P. Mojabi, Z. Wang, S. Price, Z. Lasemiimi, B. A. Besler, J. Bourqui, B. Docktor, and E. C. Fear, "Microwave breast imaging system characterization: Preliminary healthy volunteer results," in *IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Symp. Dig.*, Sep. 2023, pp. 121–123.
- [24] K. Smith, J. Bourqui, Z. Wang, B. Besler, M. Lesiuk, M. Roumeliotis, S. Quirk, P. Grendarova, J. Pinilla, S. Price, B. Docktor, and E. Fear, "Microwave imaging for monitoring breast cancer treatment: A pilot study," *Med. Phys.*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 7118–7129, Nov. 2023.
- [25] I. Correia and D. M. Godinho, "Initial study of detection and repeatability of microwave imaging with monopole antennas," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Antennas Propag. INC/USNC-URSI Radio Sci. Meeting (AP-S/INC-USNC-URSI)*, Jul. 2024, pp. 2591–2592.
- [26] C. M. Butterworth, P. Mojabi, and E. C. Fear, "Quantifying consistency of microwave breast imaging: Laser scanning for assessing breast volume and shape," *IEEE J. Electromagn., RF Microw. Med. Biol.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 335–343, Sep. 2025.
- [27] L. Egaas, A. Ikelheimer, J. Lee, D. Wong, and Z. Popović, "Repeatability of internal body temperature measurements via microwave radiometry," in *Proc. United States Nat. Committee URSI Nat. Radio Sci. Meeting (USNC-URSI NRSM)*, 2025, p. 173.
- [28] P. Mojabi, J. Bourqui, Z. Lasemiimi, B. Grewal, and E. Fear, "Microwave imaging for breast cancer detection: Performance assessment of a next-generation transmission system," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 72, no. 6, pp. 1787–1799, Jun. 2025.
- [29] A. Fasoula, P. Arvanitis, L. Duchesne, A. Fasoula, P. Arvanitis, and L. Duchesne, "Repeatability assessment of the Wavelia#2 microwave breast imaging scan: Experimental performance analysis prior to clinical investigation," in *Microwave Technologies-Recent Advances and New Trends and Applications*. London, U.K.: IntechOpen, 2023.
- [30] E. Porter, H. Bahrami, A. Santorelli, B. Gosselin, L. A. Rusch, and M. Popovic, "A wearable microwave antenna array for time-domain breast tumor screening," *IEEE Trans. Med. Imag.*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1501–1509, Jun. 2016.
- [31] M.-P. Dubuisson and A. K. Jain, "A modified Hausdorff distance for object matching," in *Proc. 12th Int. Conf. Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 1, 1994, pp. 566–568.
- [32] H. Alt and M. Godau, "Computing the fréchet distance between two polygonal curves," *Int. J. Comput. Geometry Appl.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 75–91, 1995.
- [33] L. R. Dice, "Measures of the amount of ecologic association between species," *Ecology*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 297–302, Jul. 1945.
- [34] Z. Wang, A. C. Bovik, H. R. Sheikh, and E. P. Simoncelli, "Image quality assessment: From error visibility to structural similarity," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600–612, Apr. 2004.
- [35] T. K. Koo and M. Y. Li, "A guideline of selecting and reporting intraclass correlation coefficients for reliability research," *J. Chiropractic Med.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 155–163, Jun. 2016.
- [36] J.-F. Pambrun and R. Noumeir, "Limitations of the SSIM quality metric in the context of diagnostic imaging," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Image Process. (ICIP)*, Sep. 2015, pp. 2960–2963.

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